

ExperDF-Onto: an Ontology for Promoting Controlled Experimentation in Digital Forensics

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Abstract

Experimentation is a crucial scientific method for empirical inquiry, which is also applied in Computer Science. When evaluating an artifact, it is essential to use this method to ensure reproducibility, repetition, and hypothesis testing, which clarifies the evidence of data contained in each experiment. One area in which there is a lack of a formalized experimental process is Digital Forensics (DF). This means that some of the processes are inadequate, informal, and without a proper classification of evidence, resulting in significant time expenses for their evaluation. Furthermore, existing works focused on the area often lack detailed descriptions of the experimental actions used. To support this issue, an ontology can be used to formalize the concepts and terms used in the planning and execution stages of an experiment. Hence, DF professionals working in the field require reliable instruments to ensure transparency and reproducibility in their studies. Thus, this paper presents an ontology for supporting the experimentation process in DF. The ontology was developed based on an existing conceptual model for DF experimentation, using the OWL language and class diagrams. The ontology was also evaluated by experts in experimentation and DF. The evidence presented in this study aims to contribute to the formalization of DF experimentation concepts, resulting in a standardized development of new experiments.

Keywords: Experimentation, Ontology, Digital Forensics, Evidence

1. Ontology Evaluation

1.1. Methodology Adopted

For the development of the ontology, the *TAM* methodology was used. The purpose of the methodology is to evaluate the perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) of the ontology. As for the PU, it is understood that it is the probability of using the ontology to add and improve your work, whereas the PEOU is the effort generated to use the ontology, that is, the less effort the better its ease [1]. Also, the PU and PEOU items are instigated by external variables, which are considered social, cultural, and political factors.

As for the logical impression of the researchers with the answers, as well as aiming to evaluate the agreement and disagreement of the answers, the Likert scale was used. This is a type of scale that uses psychometric responses in [2] questionnaires, in this case, based on a statement, the scale determines levels of agreement for respondents considering three fundamental elements, which are: one negative, one neutral and one positive [3]. When using this scale, different levels of measurements can be used, thus for this research, five elements were used: “I strongly disagree”, “I Disagree”, “Neutral”, “I agree”, and “I strongly agree”.

1.2. Questionnaire

The development of the ExperDF-Onto questionnaire was elaborated through combinations of the questions presented in the *TAM* method. The questionnaire was conducted by questions that comprise the *Likert* scale, in addition to having open-ended questions (Table 1).

The first section covers the PU, which is understood to be the extent of credibility that a user has in terms of performance improvement when using a [4] system. The second section refers to the PEOU, that is, the effort, whether physical or mental, to use the system, thus determining its degree of confidence [5]. In addition, we have a section that presents the open-ended questions of the questionnaire. The intention is that the participants, using their own words, can describe the adversities, favorable or negative points. In this way, it is possible to present a more detailed analysis with better qualitative data.

Table 1: Survey Questions

ID	Question
PU.1	The ontology helps me to properly document experiments in Digital Forensics.
PU.2	The ontology allows experiments in Digital Forensics to be capable of being repeated, replicated and/or reproduced.
PU.3	The ontology presents a broad view of the experimental processes in Digital Forensics and allows information retrieval.
PU.4	The Ontology classes and subclasses allow you to manage the information that evidences the findings of the experiment satisfactorily.
PU.5	With the Ontology I can apply meta-analysis to a set of Digital Forensics experiments.
PU.6	Making use of an ontology to improve the documentation of experiments is an arduous process.
PU.7	The experiments I perform can be better designed using ontology.
PU.8	The experiments I perform can be better conducted using ontology.
PU.9	The experiments I carry out can be better disseminated with the use of ontology.
PU.10	In general, I believe that ontology benefits science by formalizing the concepts and data of Digital Forensics experiments.
PEOU.1	The ontology safely and completely covers the Digital Forensics phases, providing me with security and ease of use.
PEOU.2	The ontology can be used as <i>checklist</i> in design experiments Digital Forensics.
PEOU.3	The use of properties, objects, individuals, classes, and subclasses of ontology facilitates my understanding of ontology usage.
PEOU.4	Interacting with the Ontology requires little mental effort.
PEOU.5	I find it easy to use Ontology to plan digital forensic experiments.
PEOU.6	I find it easy to use Ontology to conduct digital forensic experiments.
PEOU.7	I find it easy to use Ontology to disseminate data and evidence of Digital Forensics experiments.
PEOU.8	Overall, the Ontology is understandable and has good usability.
OQ.1	In which phase of Digital Forensics can ontology help you most in your experimentation process?
OQ.2	Would you adopt the ontology for your experiments in Digital Forensics?
OQ.3	Would you recommend this ontology to support the realization of Digital Forensics experiments?
OQ.4	Do you have suggestions, comments, or criticisms?

1.3. Execution

The experiment was carried out in stages and based on the instrumentation process. The conduction steps occurred as follows:

1. An invitation to participate in the survey was sent via e-mail;
2. The questionnaire and the science term were made available to the researchers;
3. Documents with information about classes and subclasses of the ontology and OWL files of the ontology were presented so that the participants could have access to all the elements used in the ontology;
4. The participants finished filling out the form and sent the answers.

The deadline for evaluating the ontology and answering the questionnaire was limited to 15 days. It should be noted that all follow-up to the participants was carried out *online*, via e-mail.

The objective of the study is to evaluate the reliability, viability, and effectiveness of the ontology for the controlled experimentation process in DF. For this, evaluation criteria were established so that participants could identify their purpose. In addition, all participants had access to the following documents: 1) document containing a Free and Informed Consent Form (TCLE). 2) Access to the *online* folder that contains an ontology owl file, a document with descriptions of classes and subclasses. 3) Copy of the questionnaire considered the evaluation instrument and document with ontology information.

For the execution of the questionnaire, it was understood that the best way of application would be via Google Forms ¹, with *online* answers. The form was built using the *google forms* tool and has an initial description of the search. As for the research participants, they were selected by the research area, but for convenience, not probabilistic. The form was prepared to contain:

- **Consent Form:** This is a text that anticipates the questions in the questionnaire and contains information about replicating the experiment ethically. This is a fundamental document that explains the details of the research to the participants, with their participation in a consensual and free way.
- **Respondent Characterization Questionnaire:** Seeks to collect data from participants to understand their profile, level of knowledge, and experience in DF.
- **Auxiliary Documents:** Along with the form, an OWL document with the ontology, a document that substantiates what ontology is, and a document that presents all phases of the ontology were provided. These documents are the basis for evaluating ontology, having examples through diagrams and detailed descriptions of the subject.
- **Questionnaire document:** This refers to the PU, PEOU, and Open Questions sections.

¹[acesse.one/A2Njo](https://www.google.com/forms)

Initially, the participants invited to contribute to the research were instructed to read documents that support the ontology, as they describe the use of the ontology in the planning, conduction, and dissemination of an experiment in DF through writing and diagrams. This was necessary because the ontology was based on DF phases and each one contains specific classes and subclasses that the participant can explore its functionality in the ontology.

1.4. Results

This section presents the discussion of the results of the ExperDF-Onto ontology, based on the TAM model questions, as well as considering the following aspects: (I) Perceived Usefulness (PU), (II) Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), and Open Questions (OQ). Also, it is worth noting that the answers were presented in full, without any modifications, and the abbreviation “R” is shown at the end of the text. and an integer, such as “R.1”, where which refers to the respondent number one in the survey.

1.4.1. Participants Profile

As for acting in the field of DF, 75% of respondents report that they work in academia (teacher and/or researcher), while 25% report working in academia and as an expert, agent of security, or otherwise. With regard to how long he has worked as a teacher/researcher, there is an average of 19.5 years of experience working as a teacher/researcher (Table 2). Thus demonstrating an average of considerable experience for evaluating systematic processes.

As for the location of the research target audience, 7 are from Brazil, and 1 is from the United Kingdom. Still, about the region, 5 researchers are from the southern region, 1 researcher is from the southeast region, 1 the central-west region of Brazil, and 1 researcher is from the northeast region of England. With regard to the representativeness of the areas of activity of the participants, 3 participants work exclusively in the area of Computer Forensics, 1 participant works in the areas of Computer Forensics, computational expertise, and cybernetic intelligence, 1 participant works in the area of software engineering, 1 participant works in the area of *iot* forensics and 1 participant works in the area of *network* forensics.

For the company or institution in which they act as an expert, only three participants responded, R.4 reports being a “Legal Expert”, but not specifying the role; R.6 reported acting in institutions TJMG, TJSP, TJRJ,

Table 2: Professor/Researcher Experience (in years)

Part. ID	Experience
P1	25
P2	8
P3	2
P4	30
P5	22
P6	30
P7	38
P8	1
Average	19.5
Median	23.5
St. Dev.	14

Labor Court, Federal Court and Security Forces and Law; and R.7 reports being autonomous. Still, regarding the time of experience acting as an expert, R.4 reported a performance of 5 years, R.6 of 16 years, and R.7 of 19 years.

Finally, evaluating the best characterization for the role of the participant as an expert, there were only three respondents, R.4 stated that his role as an expert is "Expert in early search of evidence on personal computers"; R.6 understands that "My work in Computational Forensics and Computational Forensics, branches of Computer Forensics, is quite diversified, over the last 16 years"; finally, R.7 best describes her function as "Expert in computational systems (software plagiarism, identification of hidden content, formation of digital evidence, among others)".

1.4.2. Perceived Usefulness

As for Perceived Usefulness (PU), it is understood that this refers to the user's perception of the performance that a given system can provide to the professional field [6]. Similarly, Mathwick et al. [7] define PU as the degree of performance needed to improve the job. This concept represents great value for adapting and reusing new technologies [8], so when considering the use of the ExperDF-Onto ontology, it can help researchers, evaluators, specialists or experts in the process of controlled experimentation in DF.

Figure 1 demonstrates that most responses are "I agree" and "Strongly agree". However, it is also notable that participant R.5 answered eight "Neutral" and R.3 four "Neutral" and four "I disagree".

Regarding questions, PU.1 questioned whether "The ontology helps me

Figure 1: Overall Perceived Usefulness (PU) results.

to properly document experiments in Digital Forensics.”. As a result, we have the following answers: 5 agree (62.5%) and 3 strongly agree (37.5%). Therefore, this demonstrates that one of the objectives of ontology, which refers to its documentation, is achieved with positive responses.

PU.2 discussed whether ”The ontology allows experiments in Digital Forensics to be repeatable, replicated and/or reproduced.”. The results show that: 5 agree (62.5%), 2 strongly agree (25%) 1 is neutral (12.5%). Although there is a percentage of 12.5% neutral, the participants understand that the ontology is efficient to replicate, repeat and reproduce experiments. Participants who understand it as neutral raise scores for detailed exploration of the discursive responses made.

PU.3 addressed whether ”- The ontology presents a broad view of the experimental processes in Digital Forensics and allows the retrieval of information.”. As result we have that: 5 agree (62.5%), 2 strongly agree (25%) and 1 is neutral (12.5%). As in the answers above, ontology proves to be efficient in parts in terms of information retrieval, but neutral results motivate thorough evaluations to better identify obstacles or ontology improvements.

PU.4 questioned whether "The classes and subclasses of the Ontology allow managing satisfactorily the information that evidences the findings of the experiment.". The results show that: 4 agree (50%), 2 strongly agree (25%), and 2 are neutral (25%). Demonstrating that most of the participants agree that ontology allows the management of information that evidences the findings of the experiment.

PU.5 questioned whether "With the Ontology I can apply meta-analysis to a set of Digital Forensics experiments.". The results indicate that 2 agree (25%), 3 strongly agree (37.5%) and 3 are neutral (37.5%). The results show that 37.5% were neutral regarding the application of meta-analysis, which should be analyzed via comparison of limitations in Subtopic 1.5.

PU.6 asked if "Using ontology to improve the documentation of experiments is an arduous process.". As result: 3 agree (37.5%), 3 strongly agree (37.5%) and 2 are neutral (25%). The results are promising and viable for documenting experiments in DF, but it is necessary to understand if there are doubts, questions, or failures for neutral participants. Thus, Subtopic 1.5 analyzes the possible limitations of this question.

PU.7 addressed whether "The experiments I perform can be better designed using the ontology.". As result: 4 strongly agree (50%), 3 are neutral (37.5%) and 1 agrees (12.5%). A little more than half of the participants understand that ontology provides better planning for experiments, indicating that ontology fulfills one of its main roles, which is to improve the way experiments are designed. However, the participants who understand it as neutral should be concerned about the results and therefore motivate a better evaluation of the discursive responses.

PU.8 asked if "The experiments I perform can be better conducted using the ontology.". As result: 3 are neutral (37.5%), 3 strongly agree (37.5%), 1 agrees (12.5%) and 1 disagrees (12.5%). Although the answers are positive regarding the use of the ontology to conduct experiments with a relevant number of participants who do not disagree, and scored as neutral, which will be evaluated the discursive scores and presented as limitations and possible improvements of the ontology.

PU.9 discussed whether "The experiments I perform can be better disseminated using the ontology.". As result: 5 agree (62.5%), 2 strongly agree (25%) and 1 is neutral (12.5%). This shows that the work carried out in the construction of the ontology is relevant and positive for the area and that the ontology provides better dissemination of experiments.

PU.10 argued that "Overall, I believe that ontology benefits science by

formalizing the concepts and data of Digital Forensics experiments.”. As result: 4 agree (50%) and 4 strongly agree (40%). its use in terms of this criterion, proving to be a viable project for the area.

1.4.3. Perceived Ease of Use

The Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) refers to the handling of the system, understanding that it does not present difficulties [6]. Rogers et al. [9] cite that PEOU is directly related to innovation, learning, and perceived use of a new tool. Dhingra and Mudgal [8] comment that innovation, as long as it is usable, confirms the amount of effort that technology contributes to better conduction of work. The author also comments that individuals who are more predisposed to the use of technologies have an easier time with usability and consequently increase [8] performance.

Figure 2 presents the graph of answers to the questions, which demonstrates that ”I agree” is present in most of the responses, highlighting PEOU.2, which refers to the use of the ontology for *check list*. It was also found that 17 respondents understood the use of the ”Neutral” response as appropriate, mainly PEOU.3, PEOU.4, and PEOU.6, and another 17 responses made use of the ”I disagree” option, highlighting PEOU.4, PEOU.6, and PEOU.8. The factors that may have an impact on these responses refer to the fact that the ontology has been extended in a minimalist way and has a large number of terms, which may require a high cognitive effort at first contact.

As for the results, PU.1 analyzed that ”The ontology safely and completely covers the phases of Digital Forensics, providing me with security and ease of use.”. Most participants understand that the ontology safely understands the DF phases, as we can see: 4 participants agree (50%), 2 are neutral (25%), 1 strongly agree (12.5%) and 1 disagrees (12.5%).

Most participants understand that, as presented in PU.2, ”The ontology can be used as a checklist in Digital Forensics experiments.”, in which 6 participants agree (75%) and 2 strongly agree (25%).

For PU.3, about ”The use of properties, objects, individuals, classes and subclasses of the ontology facilitates my understanding of the use of the ontology.”, the results show that 3 are neutral (37.5%), 2 agree (25%), 2 strongly agree (25%) and 1 disagree (20%). In this case, ontology proves to be partially important in terms of its construction using properties, objects, individuals, classes, and subclasses. It is worth understanding the neutrality and disagreement of some participants on this issue in the discussion of results.

Figure 2: Overall Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) results.

PU.4 questioning whether "Interacting with the Ontology requires little mental effort": 4 are neutral (50%), 3 disagree (37.5%) and 1 (12.5%) strongly disagree. The results demonstrate that ontology requires a high mental capacity to use. However, as this is a forensic ontology for the experimental process, the number of objects to be manipulated, not considering the application to a specific experiment, is high, which causes astonishment and interaction difficulties. Therefore, due to the negative responses, a brief discussion of the limitations and discussion of the results should be highlighted.

PU.5 asks if "I find it easy to use Ontology to plan Digital Forensics experiments.". For this question, we have: 4 disagree (50%), 2 are neutral (25%) and 2 agree (25%). The results are not favorable for the use of ontology in the planning of experiments, demonstrating that it is complex for the area, thus leaving room for discussions of the results and presentation of possible limitations.

PU.6 asks if "I find it easy to use the Ontology to conduct Digital Forensics experiments.": 3 are neutral (37.5%), 3 disagree (37.5%) and 2 agree

(25%). This question demonstrates that the ontology must be analyzed regarding its usability, since the participants, except the neutral ones, understand that it is not easy to use. As this is a negative point, it is up for discussion in the ontology results.

PU.7 questioning whether "I find it easy to use Ontology to disseminate data and evidence from Digital Forensics experiments.": 3 agree (37.5%), 2 disagree (25%), 2 are neutral (25%) and 1 strongly agree (12.5%). When evaluating the answers that agree and strongly agree, it is noted that the ontology tends to be easy to use, however, the open questions allowed us to understand the factors that led the participants to be neutral or disagree.

In the end, we have A PU.8 questioning whether "In general, the Ontology is understandable and has good usability.": 3 agree (42.9%), 3 disagree (42.9%), 1 strongly agree (12.5%) and 1 is neutral (12.5%). This demonstrates partiality regarding the understanding and use of ontology, motivating ontology exploration. However, it is also understood that factors such as the lack of an ontology instantiation example and an abstract model that could demonstrate the same in general would be great shortcuts for research participants to understand the ontology.

1.4.4. Open-ended Questions

To evaluate the open questions (OQ), the method *Grounded Theory* [10], which makes use of inference to the texts, grouping them according to consistency with the discursive responses. Therefore, through the answers, it was possible to elaborate on a consistent analysis.

OQ.1 asks "In which phase of Digital Forensics can ontology help you the most in your experimentation process?". It sought to address the phase in that ontology can best assist in experimental processes, thus making it possible to identify the following phases:

- **Collection:** One participant mentions the help of the collection phase in the experimentation process, highlighting the excerpts: "In the collection stage, the ontology part can help, as it helps a lot to identify, isolate, label and physical evidence relating to the incident being investigated." (R.1).
- **Planning or execution:** Most responses mention the planning phase, highlighted by the excerpts: "Especially in the planning and execution phases" (R.2); "I believe the ontology can be useful in planning and

reporting.” (R.4); ”I believe that in the Planning Phase, because it is possible to effectively document the elements involved in the planning, this documentation can be used throughout the experiment and also used for replication in future experiments” (R.5); ”Planning the experiments.” (R.7); ”In my point of view, the main contribution of this ontology is related to the execution phase of the experimentation process. Indicating adequate support regarding the conduction of planning and documentation, mainly of the examination, acquisition, and analysis stages.” (R.3) and ”The ontology can help me in evaluating the reference architecture for Digital Forensics tools, as well as in evaluating a future instantiation” (R.8).

- **Execution:** One participant opines about the contribution in the execution phase: ”In my point of view, the main contribution of this ontology is related to the execution phase of the experimentation process. Indicating adequate support regarding the planning conduction and documentation, mainly of the examination, acquisition, and analysis stages.”(R.3).
- **Documentation or replication:** Some participants mention the importance of the documentation or replication phase: ”I believe that the use of an Ontology is better perceived in the documentation and communication of results, as is the case of Technical Reports, in context of Incident Response, and Expert Technical Reports, in the context of Computer Forensics (Investigation and Expertise).” (R.6); and ”You can also be useful to facilitate the replication process of experiments and skills” (R.2).

OQ.2 presented the following question: ”Would you adopt the ontology for your experiments in Digital Forensics? With the answers, the following scores were identified:

- **I would adopt the ontology:** Most of the answers mention that they would adopt the ontology for the experiments, as exposed in the excerpts: ”I know the use of ontologies in other areas, I have not yet applied them in digital forensics, but I believe it should be a great experience, that after this questionnaire I will look for a way to relate them.” (R.1); ”Yes, but currently I confess that I don’t know an easy way to adopt it and I would need a clear and easy-to-use model/framework”

(R.2); "I believe so, but just from reading the text it was not clear how the process for adopting the ontology in experiments works. The ontology is very well structured, but it was not clear how to apply it." (R.3); "I would love to. But, I think it is necessary that an initial validation, with a pilot project with concrete and real data and the presentation of examples, is fundamental for a more concrete understanding of the Ontology, its instantiation in concrete examples is fundamental." (R.5); "Probably yes, since I value science, scientific methodology, and the formalization of processes and methods in conducting investigations in the context of Computer Forensics." (R.6); and "Yes, the ontology is clear and well-detailed, and can effectively help with experimentation." (R8).

- **Not applicable to the context:** A participant expresses disagreement, that is, the non-use of the ontology, this answer mentions that: "In the practice I have, the ontology does not apply completely." (R.7).
- **Neutral:** One participant did not agree or disagree with the question: "I believe that after good training in use because the initial time for understanding the ontology can be a little high." (R.4).

QQ.3 asks if "QQ.3 - Would you recommend this ontology to support the realization of Digital Forensics experiments?"

- **Use of experimentation:** Regarding the citation of ontology as a contributor to the structure of experiments, the responses stand out: "yes, to better structure the experiments, reuse knowledge" (R.2); "Yes... whenever we have tools like this, which allow us to document steps and processes, we have a powerful resource at hand, for later consultations, replication of actions taken, etc." (R.5) and "Yes, the ontology is clear and well detailed, and can effectively help with experimentation." (R8).
- **Learning process:** Some responses report on the process of understanding and learning ontology through the following excerpts: "In my opinion, I would need a better understanding, before recommending it. But as I said earlier, I believe it will be very good to use." (R.1); and "Yes, but there would be a good amount of time to learn it and be able to use it fully. The ontology can help a lot in making the process more accurate and easier to repeat, which can help a lot when building a proof ." (R.4).

- **Ontology instantiation:** One participant mentions ontology instantiation in other scenarios: "Probably yes! However, it is necessary to try it out, analyze the results and compare them with those obtained in scenarios where the Ontology was not applied." (R.5)
- **Neutral:** One participant expressed himself as neutral, giving the following answer: "Neutral, just as I evaluated in question OQ.2, there is still a lack of subsidies to evaluate the application process. costly, but from reading a use case I could better assess this issue." (R.3).

Finally, OQ.4 mentions: "Do you have suggestions, comments, or criticisms? Please, feel free to describe them".

- **Association between general elements:** Some participants cite general suggestions, through the following excerpts: "Experts generally follow their own and non-formal flows/methodologies. The use of ontologies can be an important ally to better structure experiments" (R.2); and "I encourage the continuity of this important line of research, which can produce positive impacts for Computer Forensics and Computer Science." (R.6).
- **Application examples:** Most responses express suggestions for the use of examples or means that might express their use. Therefore, we have the following answers: "Developing a visual tool for the ontology, I had difficulty identifying the information present in the figures. It is essential to the structure and discuss a use case to evaluate its application." (R.3); "In this evaluation, it would have been important to have an example of use, or even to do an experiment with the ontology to be able to have a more complete idea of the ontology. The initial time for using the ontology can be a point that prevents its use by experts already experienced and that have their process. Small real examples could demonstrate and facilitate their adoption." (R.4); and "Present examples of ontology instantiation, to facilitate understanding by those who want to use it," (R.5).
- **Ontological scenario restriction:** There is an opinion expressed about minimizing the ontology, restricting your scenario to something more specific: "The main suggestion is to focus on ontologies aimed at sub-specialization by sub-areas and not to try an ontology generic for

all areas of Digital Forensics. There are situations in which an ontology may not be useful or applicable from a practical day-to-day point of view, mainly in Forensic Computer Sections (whether State Scientific Police or Federal Police), this is to the existing workload.” (R.7).

- **Neutral:** One participant expresses himself as neutral, inferring that: ”Just a caveat, I still don’t use ontology in forensics, so I don’t feel comfortable giving an opinion at this time.” (R.1).

1.5. Discussion of Results

Based on the participants’ responses, it is possible to present evidence on important points of discussion, such as the case of PU, which, in general, presents good results for PU.1, PU.2, PU.3, PU.4, PU.9 and PU.10. More than half of the PU questions have positive answers regarding the use of ontology in documentation, replication, data visualization, information management, dissemination and formalization of concepts. All six PU mentioned have favorable results above 57%.

However, regarding the questions, PU.5, PU.6, PU.7, and PU.8 that are related to the application of meta-analysis, use of ontology, planning, and conduction of experiments, the answers do not present satisfactory results and that, as a rule, it is related to the non-presentation of an ontology instantiation example to the participants, which made it difficult to understand the execution, planning, and conduction of experiments. Without a model instantiation, the participants had limitations to imagine an example of using the classes and subclasses that could be instantiated.

For the questions of PU.2, PU.3, PU.4, PU.5, PU.6, PU.7, PU.8, and PU.9 that there are understandings as neutral, the following hypotheses can be discussed: a) R.5 acts directly in the research field and does not have experience in a company or institution, in addition, the field of action is engineering, not entering the context of ontologies. Therefore, the choice of neutral best fits your context for the question of PU.2, PU.3, and PU.7; b) For the other questions, it is understood that the proposed ontology does not have a practical example of use an instance, therefore, formulating an abstract theoretical example without data for the ontology means that the participants cannot understand its totality of gain; and c) The lack of a document explaining how to use each ontology class in practice can induce neutral responses, since, in an application or instantiation context, not all elements of the ontology will be used, but only those that make sense for the

scenario of the application. This reduces the amount of effort in using the ontology, for example, if a normality test is not applied to the experiment because it has no context, all its instances must be disregarded, simplifying the number of elements to be used.

For the issue of PU, it is considered that PU.1, PU.2 show good results in terms of safety for use in the DF phases, as well as their use as a checklist in an experiment. Safety is evidenced regarding the DF phases with responses above 57.1%, which are important data that prove how efficient the ontology, used properly, is for evaluations of forensic experimental processes. However, some points raised in PU.3, PU.4, PU.5, PU.6, PU.7, and PU.8 demonstrate that the ontology also has limitations regarding the use of properties, interactions, planning, and conducting of experiments and its usability.

Initially, it is important to highlight that this is an ontology for the experimentation process in DF, that is, it does not cover a specific area within the DF, but its general contexts. As it is an ontology that extends an already proposed model, the number of elements, that is, original classes and subclasses plus the extendable ones, leaves the ontology spacious. This causes the ontology to present many concepts, relationships, classes, and others, which had an impact on the negative evaluations, since its visualization was presented in parts by diagrams, thus not having a complete view of all the information at the time of carrying out the analysis search.

With regard to OQ, the responses demonstrate that the ontology actually helps in the experimentation process in DF, in addition to the fact that it can be adopted and recommended to support the experimental process, being one of the important points of the research. This shows that the use of an ontology helps to better define relationships, processes, and concepts used during an experiment, thus making the conduct of experiments more formal, as well as showing better results in the final reports of an expert, oncologist, or researcher.

It is emphasized, therefore, that all points of improvement exposed by the participants are important to refine the ontology, such as the presentation of examples, creation of a *framework*, and the focus on the specialization of a subarea of DF. These points can facilitate both the usability and the ontology dissemination process.

In summary, the questionnaire with its objective and discursive questions exposed a timely view of the ontology, it also helped to identify points of improvement, inconsistencies, and expansion of future discussions about new implementations for ExperDF-Onto.

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